

THE PUBLIC SPEAKING PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 12 LEARNERS IN DIFFERENT COMMUNICATIVE DOMAIN

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 27

Issue 2

Pages: 204-212

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2553

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14005934

Manuscript Accepted: 10-12-2024

The Public Speaking Performance of Grade 12 Learners in Different Communicative Domain

Contessa Carla P. Alcazar*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study aimed to determine the public speaking performance in different communicative domains of Grade 12 learners in Angono National High School, during the school year 2020-2021. The Public Speaking Guideline (PSG) was developed and validated based on the learner's level of understanding. In rating the acceptability of the material, a partially- adapted checklist was utilized. To evaluate the public speaking performance, a researcher-made rubrics was employed and evaluated by English teachers from other schools and Angono National High School. Descriptive-developmental research method was used in the study. The participants were composed of two (2) sections of Grade 12 who were enrolled in the Online Distance Learning (ODL) modality, particularly HUMSS A and HUMSS B. The participants were selected using the equating variables in Oral Communication subject. A diagnostic test was given to assess the learners in terms of communicative domains and online communicative events used in public speaking. The Public Speaking Guideline was validated by the experts and was found acceptable in terms of objective, content, language used, usefulness and presentation. Based on the findings, it was found that the learners were able to deliver comprehensible ideas yet had difficulty on the use of articulation, modulation, gestures and movement. In addition, the study revealed that student's interest was stimulated when exposed to various communicative event which led to a meaningful interaction that created a positive impact on learner's speaking performance.

Keywords: *public speaking, communicative domain, Grade 12*

Introduction

One of the most important job-related skills that employers seek in the global market today is speaking. The ability to converse efficiently with the use of the English language is considered more important than writing and math skills, as well as other qualities such as initiative, technical competence, and organizational abilities.

This significant demand in the workplace creates a huge impact on the role of the teacher in producing knowledgeable, competent, driven, and globally competitive individuals through quality education. To realize this goal, the activities employed by the teacher in the learning process to hone the speaking skills of 21st-century learners must be substantial and appropriate to their level and needs.

Moreover, speaking is more than just an expression but a reflection of an individual's personality, self-image, knowledge, and ability to reason out and express ideas clearly and excellently using the English language.

In a survey conducted by the National Association of Colleges and Employers in 2016, communication skills ranked as one of the most important personal qualities employers seek in an employee. This quality is beneficial in enhancing international relations and cultural understanding.

In the Philippines, English is considered the second language because it is widely used in daily communication and transactions. Despite the exposure of the learners to the use of the language, it was found in the competency mapping administered by the Department of Science and Technology (DOST) with the use of the IT & Business Process Association of the Philippines (IBPAP) industry-grade Global Competency Assessment Tool that the broadest competency gap between what the IT business industry needs and what the graduates have is in English proficiency.

A similar scenario was manifested in the McKinsey & Company study published in Forbes magazine as cited by Rapoza (2015), stating that only 13 percent of graduates from emerging countries are suited for employment in global companies and the primary reason is a lack of English skills.

To meet the international standard of education, the government implemented RA10533, known as the "Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013"—the advent of the Senior High School Curriculum. This aims to produce graduates who are equipped with essential competencies, skills, and values for life-long learning and employment as it provides four curriculum exits, namely: higher education, middle-level development, entrepreneurship, and employment.

For this reason, students were anticipated to acquire the necessary competency to become proficient English speakers since one of the core subjects offered is Oral Communication, which focuses on the development of students' listening and speaking skills. This includes the application of different skills and strategies for effective communication in various situations. Moreover, this helps the learner understand the importance of acquiring good communication skills that are applicable to real-life situations.

The researcher has seen students struggle with constructing logical ideas to clearly emphasize important details during a dialogue. Awkwardness was demonstrated in speaking the English language, even in pronouncing unfamiliar and difficult words in front of the class. This can be perceived in different subject areas when the students are prompted to conduct reports and school presentations.

It was in this context that the researcher believed that the developed public speaking guidelines could supplement the gap in the use of the English language and enhance the speaking skills among learners.

The researcher believes that the public speaking guidelines can bridge the gap and improve the inadequacy of speaking performances among learners. It was also anticipated that supplementary material could be utilized by teachers to motivate the learners to participate in varied speaking activities, be it on online platforms or traditional teaching activities.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the public speaking performance of Grade 12 learners at Angono National High School during the school year 2020–2021 in accordance with the different communicative domains. It sought to answer the following questions:

1. What was the public speaking performance of Grade 12 learners in the different communicative domains in terms of:
 - 1.1. content;
 - 1.2. articulation;
 - 1.3. modulation;
 - 1.4. gestures and movements?
2. What was the public speaking performances of the Grade 12 learners in terms of:
 - 2.1. language acquisition;
 - 2.2. language learning; and
 - 2.3. language structure?
3. What was the public speaking performances of the Grade 12 learners with respect to Online Communicative event in terms of:
 - 3.1. elevator pitch;
 - 3.2. infomercial; and
 - 3.3. photo story telling?
4. How did the experts evaluate the developed output of the Grade 12 learners with respect to:
 - 4.1. objective;
 - 4.2. content;
 - 4.3. language used;
 - 4.4. usefulness; and
 - 4.5. presentation?

Literature Review

Public speaking is the act of conveying information to an audience intended for a specific purpose. This form of communication allows the speaker and the audience to build connections that can influence decisions and motivate change.

In this study, "public speaking" refers to the performance utilized by the researcher to determine the speaking skills of the learners.

Verderber, Sellnow, and Verderber (2011) defined public speaking as a sustained formal presentation by a speaker to an audience and a form of human communication.

According to Dayon (2019), in a public speaking context, a great public speaker needs to know how to perform their speech at the appropriate level. This implies that there is a need for the speaker to understand the goal of speaking to an audience.

In a study conducted by Dela Cruz (2019) entitled "Communicative Competencies and Pre-Service Teaching Performance: Basis for Communication Skills Enhancement", it was found that pre-service teachers enrolled in BEED-General Curriculum have an above-average level of communicative competencies in reading, listening, and writing but only an average level of communicative competencies in speaking. Thus, a need to enhance the communicative competencies, especially in speaking and writing, was identified. An integrated listening, speaking, reading, and writing (LSRW) program for enhancement of the pre-service teachers' (PST) communicative competencies was proposed.

Meanwhile, Alaya-ay (2012) found that articulation mistakes decrease, and social skills increase as the age of the children increases. Furthermore, children with articulation disorders have lower social skills than children without articulation disorders, and speech is one of the factors that affect social ranking.

Relatively, Arcilla et al. (2017) highlighted in his study the need to conduct an analysis on students' phonological articulation abilities in English by incorporating more creative and meaningful drill activities. The said drill is intended to address the difficulty of learners in pronouncing English sounds.

On the other hand, in a study entitled Voice Modulation in Human Mate Choice, Sorokowsk et al. (2019), it was found that vocal behavior varies and can be affected when a person interacts at an individual and group level—mate preference. In addition, human voice modulation functions in non-verbal communication to elicit favorable judgements and behaviors from others, including potential mates.

Moreover, Kang and Tversky (2016) in a study entitled "From hands to minds: Gestures promote Understanding" revealed that seeing gestures representing actions enhances understanding of the dynamics of a complex system as revealed in invented language, gestures, and visual explanations. In addition, it was highlighted that gestures can map many meanings more directly than language, representing many concepts congruently. This means that designing and using gestures similar in meaning can enhance comprehension and learning.

Methodology

Research Design

In accomplishing this study, the researcher utilized the descriptive developmental method of research to determine the public speaking performance of Grade 12 learners in the different communicative domains as a response to the objectives of this study.

This study utilized a descriptive-developmental method of research. Gillaco (2014) stated that the descriptive method seeks real facts in relation to a current situation that works primarily on the description, comparison, analysis, and interpretation of data that exists.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the selected Grade 12 learners from Angono National High School under the K-12 Curriculum during the School Year 2020–2021.

Among the seventy-one (71) learners from the two sections under the online distance learning modality class, thirty (30) learners have an equating variable in the final average grade in Oral Communication with a range from 85 to 89.

Furthermore, the respondents of the study were not directly handled by the researcher. There were fifteen (15) participants from HUMSS A and fifteen (15) participants from HUMSS B who were handled by the two (2) experts in English who acted as evaluators in the study. Both evaluators were experts in the field of English and were graduates of Master of Arts in Teaching English at the University of Rizal System and are presently studying for a Doctor of Philosophy Major in English at the University of Perpetual Help-Delta.

Instrument

The data utilized to determine the public speaking performance of the grade 12 learners in different communicative domains was formed with the utilization of the researcher-made rubrics and the speaking component of the respondents.

Moreover, the researcher-made rubrics were validated and used to evaluate the public speaking performance in different communicative domains in terms of the content and speech delivery principles such as articulation, modulation, gestures and movement, language acquisition, language learning, and language structure.

Procedure

The study began with the analysis of the problem, which aims to determine the public speaking performance of selected Grade 12 learners in the different communicative domains. Apart from this, the availability of online distance learning as a teaching modality was also considered in the progress of the study. Moreover, a diagnostic test was given to assess the communicative domains and online communicative events like infomercials, elevator pitches, and photo story telling used for public speaking.

Further, the researcher made a Public Speaking Guidelines or Project PSG provided with mechanics, rubrics, and video presentation with a longer time frame to complete the public speaking performance of the learners with the use of the English language. This Project PSG was evaluated by ten (10) English teachers from the Humanities and Social Sciences Strand utilizing the partially adapted checklist.

Next, the researcher prepared the tools to be used for the study. The selection and preparation of public speaking activities were consulted and agreed upon by the English teachers and the researcher. The crafting of researcher-made rubrics and the modification of partially adapted checklists was done and validated to conform to the objective of the study, which is necessary for the next procedure.

Moreover, the researcher conducted three (3) consecutive Saturday classes via Google Meet, to discuss and use the Project PSG or Public Speaking Guidelines to help the participants deliver the three (3) public speaking performances in elevator pitch, infomercial, and photo storytelling.

Using the Google Forms, the speaking skills of Grade 12 learners at Angono National High School with respect to different communicative domains such as: content, articulation, modulation, gestures, and movements. Then for public speaking performances of Grade 12 learners, were properly evaluated.

The final phase was the analysis of the public speaking performance of the grade 12 learners and the assessment of the modified instructional material that is subjected to further development and revision.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Profile of the Teacher-Respondents and Student-Respondents

Table 1. *Public Speaking Performance of Grade 12 Learners in the Different Communicative Domains in terms of Content*

	<i>Content</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	Was relevant and appropriate to the audience.	4.00	Excellent
2.	Was clear and well-defined.	3.78	Excellent
3.	Was organized and logically arranged.	3.83	Excellent
4.	Supported with valid and credible sources.	3.93	Excellent
5.	Emphasized the main point of ideas.	3.95	Excellent
	Overall	3.90	Excellent

The participants were able to emphasize the main points of the idea by providing valid and credible sources, as shown by the overall mean of 3.90 and verbally interpreted as excellent, in which the speaker provided an outstanding execution in the presentation of ideas. The data imply that the participants were able to generate relevant and appropriate content for the audience through the use of the Public Speaking Guidelines, which is an integral component of a speaking performance.

The findings above correlate with the study of Tuazon (2018), emphasizing that content is the substantial output expressed and developed by the student on a particular topic assigned to them.

Table 2. *Public Speaking Performance of Grade 12 Learners in the Different Communicative Domains in terms of Articulation*

	<i>Articulation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	Was clearly pronounced and enunciated.	3.87	Excellent
2.	Had absence of vocal fillers (uhm, ah).	3.75	Excellent
3.	Had correct word choice and grammar.	3.92	Excellent
4.	Had proper form of /p/, /f/, /v/ and /b/ sound.	3.83	Excellent
5.	Can be easily understood.	3.93	Excellent
	Overall	3.86	Excellent

As depicted in the table, the performance of the Grade 12 Humanities and Social Sciences participants in terms of articulation was excellent, with an overall mean of 3.86, which indicates that the speaker had an exceptional performance in the use of articulation, pronunciation, and grammar. This indicates that through the varied activities in the Public Speaking Guidelines, the participants were able to deliver comprehensible ideas to the audience.

This was linked in the study by Arcilla (2017), emphasizing the need to incorporate a more creative and meaningful drill activity to develop the learners' articulation ability.

Table 3. *Public Speaking Performance of Grade 12 Learners in the Different Communicative Domains in terms of Modulation*

	<i>Modulation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	Was well-paced and has varied rate or speed.	3.88	Excellent
2.	Used 'pause' to effectively emphasize an idea.	3.87	Excellent
3.	Had an audible and pleasant sound.	3.83	Excellent
4.	Was well-adjusted to audience size.	3.95	Excellent
5.	Used a non-monotone voice	3.95	Excellent
	Overall	3.90	Excellent

The result shows that the Grade 12 participants in Humanities and Social Sciences had an outstanding execution of their public speaking performance in terms of modulation, as shown by their overall mean of 3.90. This implies that the participants exposed in the use of the Public Speaking Guidelines have effectively applied the use of modulation in the delivery of a speaking performance.

This accords to the findings of Manalo (2017) that voice modulation can be used to highlight the key points within the presentation and retain the attention of the audience as the voice carries a lot of weight in the delivery of the message.

Table 4. *Public Speaking Performance of Grade 12 Learners in the Different Communicative Domains in terms of Gestures and Movements*

	<i>Gestures and Movements</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	Showed established and maintained eye contact.	3.87	Excellent
2.	Had the absence of distracting movement or mannerism.	3.82	Excellent
3.	Displayed gestures, posture and facial expressions that was expressive, dynamic and natural.	3.88	Excellent
4.	Displayed appropriateness in attire.	3.83	Excellent
5.	Showed mastery of the speech.	3.95	Excellent
	Overall	3.87	Excellent

This means that the use of non-verbal communication was well- established and well-maintained as reflected on the overall mean of 3.97 with a verbal interpretation of excellent in which the use of eye contact, expressive, dynamic and natural way of expression were exceptionally demonstrated. This signifies that gesture and movement, as emphasized in the Public Speaking Guideline, are an integral part of speech delivery as they mirror the spoken and unspoken thoughts of the speaker, which serves as a window of cognition.

This was supported by the study conducted by Araya (2016), stating that gesture is a fundamental component of language that contributes meaningful and unique information to a spoken message that reflects the speaker's underlying knowledge and experiences.

Language Acquisition, Language Learning, and Language Structure of Grade 12 Learners' Public Speaking Performance

Table 5. *Public Speaking Performance of Grade 12 Learners in terms of Language Acquisition*

<i>Language Acquisition</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. The meaningful communication was evident.	3.98	Excellent
2. The idea was expressed easily and naturally.	3.73	Excellent
3. The meaning of the utterance was emphasized.	3.90	Excellent
4. The understanding of language was existent.	3.90	Excellent
5. The practice of language use was noticeable.	3.93	Excellent
Overall	3.89	Excellent

Evidence shows that the Grade 12 Humanities and Social Sciences participants achieved an overall mean of 3.89 with a verbal interpretation of excellent in their public speaking performance in terms of language acquisition. The outcome displays the positive impact of the Public Speaking Guidelines as it fosters meaningful communication in the speaking performance of the participants. It indicates that when the learner understands the existing language, they can create meaningful interaction and further emphasizes an idea in which the enhancement of speaking skills is being promoted and enhanced.

Azimi (2012) highlighted that conversation practice helps in second language acquisition. remarking that second-language learners benefit from working on tasks with high communicative value with the goal of achieving successful social interaction and communication.

Table 6. *Public Speaking Performance of Grade 12 Learners in terms of Language Learning*

<i>Language Learning</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. The logical arrangement of words was applied.	3.88	Excellent
2. The structure of the utterance was predictable.	3.82	Excellent
3. The consciousness in grammar was manifested.	3.87	Excellent
4. The correctness of grammar and language was evident.	3.85	Excellent
5. The knowledge in the form of language was present.	3.88	Excellent
Overall	3.86	Excellent

On the table presented, the overall mean of 3.86 and verbal interpretation of excellent in the public speaking performance of the Grade 12 Humanities and Social Sciences participants in terms of language learning can be observed. This reflects that, through the use of the Public Speaking Guidelines, the participants were able to demonstrate and apply their knowledge of the form of language as manifested in the logical arrangement of words and ideas during the speaking performance.

Bartolo (2019) emphasized that producing language during learning can improve comprehension, language representations, and educational practices, which creates an incredibly strong learning experience that involves generating the language and providing feedback.

Table 7. *Public Speaking Performance of Grade 12 Learners in terms of Language Structure*

<i>Language Structure</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. The proper combination and order of words was noticeable.	3.90	Excellent
2. The ideas presented were free from error from grammatical structure.	3.73	Excellent
3. The meaning of the utterance can be clearly understood.	3.95	Excellent
4. The wide range use of vocabulary was evident.	3.75	Excellent
5. The correct and appropriate vocabulary was applied.	3.88	Excellent
Overall	3.84	Excellent

The table presents the public speaking performance of the Grade 12 Humanities and Social Sciences participants in terms of language structure, with an overall mean of 3.84 and verbal interpretation of excellent. This reflects that knowledge of language structure, particularly with the use of grammar and wide use of appropriate vocabulary, was developed through the use of the Public Speaking

Guidelines. The concept was supported by Muyalde (2018), highlighting that one of the influential factors in attaining communicative skills is the lingua franca used in media and technology, both at international and local level, to which the 21st generation is exposed.

Public Speaking Performance of Performance of Grade 12 Learners

Table 8. *Public Speaking Performance of Performance of Grade 12 Learners with respect to Online Communicative Event in terms of Elevator Pitch*

<i>Elevator Pitch</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
Compelling		
1. The speaker enticed the audience during the pitch	3.98	Excellent
Informative		
1. The speaker delivered all the important details expected during the pitch. (self-introduction, statement of purpose, qualification)	3.83	Excellent
Delivery		
1. The speaker demonstrated professionalism	3.93	Excellent
2. The speaker utilized voice projection	3.80	Excellent
Overall	3.89	Excellent

The outcome shows that the G12 Humanities and Social Sciences participants attained an overall mean score of 3.89 with a verbal interpretation of excellent in their elevator pitch activity. This signifies that elevator pitch activity incorporated into the Public Speaking Guideline is suitable to the needs of the participants, which can further promote speaking skills and adaptability in any speaking situation.

According to Romero et al. (2017), in his study entitled "Flipped Learning with Elevator Pitch and Pecha Kucha," they found out that the use of elevator pitch showed great student interest and good skills that led to a deeper and stronger understanding of matters and proved more competence acquisition.

Table 9. *Public Speaking Performance of Performance of Grade 12 Learners with respect to Online Communicative Event in terms of Infomercial*

<i>Infomercial</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
Relevance: The speaker's performance was relevant to the theme	3.95	Excellent
Creativity and Originality		
1. The speaker presented an infomercial relative to the theme	3.85	Excellent
2. The speaker the infomercial in a unique way	3.85	Excellent
3. The speaker presented the infomercial in a creative and imaginative way	3.90	Excellent
Average	3.87	Excellent
Audience Impact		
1. The speaker evoked emotion to viewers	3.90	Excellent
2. The speaker kept the viewers engage without losing momentum	4.00	Excellent
Average	3.95	Excellent
Overall	3.92	Excellent

It can be gleaned from the table that the Grade 12 Humanities and Social Sciences participants were able to deliver a superb performance of the Infomercial activity, with a mean score of 3.92 and a verbal interpretation of excellent. This implies that the informational activity outlined in the Public Speaking Guideline fits the demand to aid the development of the speaking skills of the participants.

In the study of Armand (2016) entitled "Promoting Critical Thinking and Self-expression with Student Infomercial," it was found that learners were able to foster the development of creative thinking and communicative language skills when engaged in the analysis, development, and production of the infomercial.

Table 10. *Public Speaking Performance of Performance of Grade 12 Learners in Online Communicative Event in terms of Photo Story Telling*

<i>Photo Story Telling</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
Story	3.85	Excellent
1. The speaker presented a clear narrative of the story	3.80	Excellent
2. The speaker presented well-developed characters, places, and events	3.95	Excellent
3. The speaker employed creativity with the use of language	3.87	Excellent
Average	3.87	Excellent
Interpretation		
1. The speaker conveyed original and well-developed story	3.85	Excellent
2. The speaker allowed the listener to re-imagine the story	3.95	Excellent
3. The speaker used appropriate emotion in telling the story	3.90	Excellent
Average	3.90	Excellent
Overall	3.88	Excellent

The table denotes the overall mean of 3.88 and verbal interpretation of excellent in the Photo Storytelling Performance of the Grade 12 Humanities and Social Sciences participants. It can be inferred that the Photo Storytelling activity employed in the Public Speaking Guidelines enhanced the participants' capacity to nurture creativity in the delivery of the speaking performance.

Jianing (2007) highlighted that using storytelling in an English classroom is one of the best activities to encourage students to study English.

Table 11. *Expert's Evaluation of the Developed Output in Public Speaking of Grade 12 Learners with respect to Objectives*

	<i>Objective</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	The objectives of the activity are explained clearly.	4.80	Very Much Attained
2.	The objectives of the activity are attained.	4.80	Very Much Attained
3.	The objectives of each activity are measured.	4.80	Very Much Attained
4.	The objectives of the activity are based on the learning abilities of the learners.	4.80	Very Much Attained
5.	The objectives of the activity are properly allocated according to the degree of competencies.	4.80	Very Much Attained
Overall		4.80	Very Much Attained

The table reveals that the researcher's validated output for the Grade 12 participants contains activities that have a clear, attainable, and measurable objective that focuses on the development of learning abilities and competencies. The output has a verbal interpretation of very much attained with an overall mean of 4.80. It shows that the objectives of the developed output are appropriate to the level and ability of the Grade 12 participants, as it shows a clear manifestation of the attainment of specific learning competencies.

Tuazon (2018) highlighted in his study that activities in any subject must have objectives to guide the teachers in accomplishing their work.

Table 12. *Evaluation of the Expert's on the Developed Output in Public Speaking of Grade 12 Learners with respect to Content*

	<i>Content</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	The content is appropriate in the needs of the learners.	4.90	Very Highly Sufficient
2.	The content is accurate and precise.	4.80	Very Highly Sufficient
3.	The content has an appropriate method and clear directions to follow.	4.90	Very Highly Sufficient
4.	The content is relevant to the needs of the students.	4.90	Very Highly Sufficient
5.	The content contributes to meet the objectives.	4.90	Very Highly Sufficient
Overall		4.88	Very Highly Sufficient

It can be obtained from the table that an expert's validation on the developed output of Grade 12 learners with respect to content attained a verbal interpretation of Very Highly Sufficient (VHS) with an overall mean score of 4.88. As revealed, the content of the material is appropriate to the needs of the learners. This implies that the content is valid, appropriate, and congruent to the intellectual level of the learners. The material is comprehensible and sufficient to address the needs of the learner to execute the given task.

The study by Balasta et al. (2010) entitled, Development and Validation of Manipulative Activities in Teaching Social Skills among Children with Autism, was found to be very much accepted by the respondents, specifically in terms of its content.

Table 13. *Evaluation of the Expert's on the Developed Output in Public Speaking of Grade 12 Learners with respect to Language Used*

	<i>Language Used</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	The language used is basic and simple and easy to comprehend.	4.80	Very Much Appropriate
2.	The language and style contained correct and reliable information.	4.80	Very Much Appropriate
3.	The language used is suitable to the ability of the learners.	4.80	Very Much Appropriate
4.	The language gives clear information about the topic.	4.80	Very Much Appropriate
5.	The language is within the learning levels of students.	4.80	Very Much Appropriate
Overall		4.80	Very Much Appropriate

The results insinuate that the experts agreed on the validity of the language used in the developed output of Grade 12 learners with an overall mean of 4.80 and verbal interpretation of Very Much Appropriate (VMA). As shown in the table above, the language used was simple, comprehensible, and appropriate to the learning levels of the students.

Orbeta & San Jose (2013) mentioned in his study that the language used in the teaching materials should be understood by the learners. He emphasized that a well written material should be clear, simple and orderly to make learning and comprehension easy at the same time entertaining.

The table 14 presents the expert's validation on the usefulness of the developed output of the Grade 12 learners with an overall mean percentage of 4.70 and a verbal interpretation of very much useful (VMU). The output reflects the validity of the usefulness of the material as it strengthens the better facilitation of learning and the development of the learner's speaking skills. It suggests that the usefulness of the material is compatible with the level of grade 12 students since it provides an opportunity to explore varied speaking performances.

Table 14. *Expert's Evaluation of the Developed Output in Public Speaking of Grade 12 Learners with respect to Usefulness*

	<i>Usefulness</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	The prepared activities intensify student's learning.	4.70	Very Much Useful
2.	The prepared activities are relevant to the lesson.	4.70	Very Much Useful
3.	The prepared activities are interesting and well presented.	4.70	Very Much Useful
4.	The prepared activities facilitate better understanding of the lesson.	4.70	Very Much Useful
5.	The prepared activities can stimulate enthusiasm to do the task.	4.70	Very Much Useful
	Overall	4.70	Very Much Useful

It can be derived from the table 15 that the English teachers find the developed output of grade 12 learners with respect to presentation as very much organized in verbal interpretation with an overall mean of 4.70. It can be interpreted that the presentation of the developed output arouses the learner's interest and reinforces the transfer of learning. Clarity of presentation allows better understanding of methods that are necessary for the level of the learners.

Table 15. *Evaluation of the Expert's on the Developed Output in Public Speaking of Grade 12 Learners with respect to Presentation*

	<i>Presentation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	The presentation of the guidebook reinforces the transfer of learning.	4.70	Very Much Organized
2.	The methods used were appropriate for the level of the learners.	4.70	Very Much Organized
3.	Illustrations and figures were well presented.	4.70	Very Much Organized
4.	The presentation arouses the student's interest and motivates the students.	4.70	Very Much Organized
5.	The presentation exhibited clarity of presentation.	4.70	Very Much Organized
	Overall	4.70	Very Much Organized

The findings support the study of (2018) that the system of instruction can be easily followed by the learners because the organization of presentation was systematic in which the developed learning package became an effective instrument in the teaching-learning process and proven organized.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

Although the participants can speak comprehensible ideas, they should continue to practice articulation, modulation, gestures, and movement to improve their speaking skills.

Meaningful interaction created a positive impact on the participants' speaking skills, as reflected in their public speaking performance, where the knowledge and use of language structure were evident in the delivery.

Online Communicative Events such as Elevator Pitch, Infomercial, and Photo Story Telling stimulated participants' interest in different public speaking performances.

The developed Public Speaking Guidelines (PSG) assist participants in developing their speaking skills by exposing them to a variety of public speaking performances.

The developed Public Speaking Guidelines (PSG) were innovative and relevant in developing the public speaking skills of the participants, yet the need for inclusion of authentic activities is encouraged for further studies related to the topic.

References

- Alaya-ay, G. (2012). Storytelling through Video: A Bilingual Approach in Teaching. *IAMURE International Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(1). Retrieved from <http://ejournals.ph/form/cite.php?id=586>.
- Araya, J. (2016). Scaffolding Writing Competence Through Process Writing and Error Correction. *LAMDAG*, 7(1). Retrieved from <http://ejournals.ph/form/cite.php?id=11477>.
- Arcilla Jr. F. E., Soriano, E. J. A., Bayeta, P. L. B. (2017) First Language Influence on Second Language Phonology Among Visayan Speakers *IAMURE International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research* ⇒ vol. 16 no. 1.
- Azimi, M..(2012). Grammar in the Language Classroom: A Case Study of Teachers' Attitudes and their Actual Behaviour in the Class. *IAMURE International Journal of Education*, 2(1). Retrieved from <http://ejournals.ph/form/cite.php?id=3119>.
- Bartolo, E. (2019). "Well... Y'know... Okay..." An Analysis of Discourse Markers' Pragmatic Functions and Sentence Positions among Senior High School English Teachers' Spoken Discourse: Implications for Language Teaching. *The ASTR Research Journal*, 3(1). Retrieved from <http://ejournals.ph/form/cite.php?id=14884>.
- Dayon, C. (2019). Semantic Feature Of Philippine English: A Qualitative Analysis. *Southeast Asian Journal of Teaching and*

Innovation, 1(1). Retrieved from <http://ejournals.ph/form/cite.php?id=14490>.

Dela Cruz, Lilian B. (2019), Communicative Competencies and Pre-Service Teaching Performance: Basis for Communication Skills Enhancement, JPAIR Multidisciplinary Research Journal, vol. 38 no. 1.

Kang S. & Tversky, B. (2016) From hands to minds: Gestures promote understanding Cognitive Research: Principles and Implications volume 1, Article number: 4 <https://cognitiveresearchjournal.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s41235-016-0004-9>.

Manalo, O. (2017). “Speech Communication Skills and Voice Quality of Morong National High School Senior Students”, Unpublished Master’s Thesis, University of Rizal System, Morong, Rizal.

Muyalde, J. (2018). Preferred Learning Styles and Language Instructional Techniques of Grade 11 Students and their English Language Proficiency. Tin-aw, 2(1). Retrieved from <http://ejournals.ph/form/cite.php?id=13635>.

Orbeta, E. & San Jose, A. (2013). Apprehension in Language Learning Anxiety as Significant Correlate of Oral Performance in English of College Freshmen. IAMURE International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research, 5(1). Retrieved from <http://ejournals.ph/form/cite.php?id=2536>.

Rapoza, K. (2015). Countries with The Best Business, English <https://www.forbes.com/sites/kenrapoza/2012/04/05/countries-with-the-best-business-english/?sh=228c8da33997>.

Sorokowsk, P., Puts, D., Johnson, J., Żółkiewicz, O. Oleszkiewicz, A. Sorokowska, A., Kowal, M., Borkowska, B., Pisanski, K. (2019) Voice of Authority: Professionals Lower Their Vocal Frequencies When Giving Expert Advice Journal of Nonverbal Behavior (2019) 43:257–269 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10919-019-00307-0>.

Tuazon, D. (2018). “The Use of Multimedia Instructional Materials as Innovative e-Teaching Strategy for Grade”, Unpublished Master’s Thesis, University of Rizal System, Morong, Rizal.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Contessa Carla P. Alcazar

Angono National High School

Department of Education – Philippines